

Appraisal Records of the Edo Period

Tan'yū Shukuzu (Plum, Bamboo, and Fruit Scroll) by Kanō Tan'yū

Mayumi Ono

Introduction

Kanō Tan'yū (1602–1674) conducted numerous appraisals of ancient paintings throughout his lifetime. In his evaluations, he documented his observations alongside small-scale reproductions, collectively known as *Tan'yū Shukuzu*. These records have been preserved in various institutions and private collections, both domestically and internationally.¹ The Tokyo National Museum also holds several examples of *Tan'yū Shukuzu*,² among which one notable scroll, titled *Baichiku Kashi* (*Plum, Bamboo, and Fruit*) (A-9961, hereinafter referred to as the *Baichiku Kashi Scroll*), will be the focus of this study.

The *Baichiku Kashi Scroll* measures 28.0 cm in height and 1711.0 cm in length and is executed on paper with colored pigments. The scroll is composed of sheets of paper, each approximately 14 cm in height, arranged in two rows. A full reproduction of the scroll, along with transcriptions of the annotations, is provided at the end of this article, with sequential numbering added to the paper joints for reference.³ Originally, *Tan'yū Shukuzu* were arranged in the chronological order of appraisal; however, following their dispersal from the Kajibashi Kanō family (a lineage founded by Tan'yū), they were later reassembled and have survived in their current form. As a result, some sketches may include fragments executed by artists other than Tan'yū, making detailed analysis—particularly of the annotations—essential.⁴

The *Baichiku Kashi Scroll* contains 40 sketches of plum trees, 57 sketches of bamboo, and 66 sketches of fruits, arranged by subject rather than in chronological sequence. Unfortunately, even when annotations include terms such as "same year" or "same", precise production dates are often absent. In terms of appraisal, many works are labeled with phrases like "筆不知" (meaning 'brush unknown') or "正筆ニテなし" ('not an authentic brushwork'), indicating that their authors remain unidentified. However, some

sketches exhibit significant connections to existing works. This article will first examine these connections before introducing the identified owners of the works. Additionally, we will highlight descriptions that offer insight into Tan'yū's appraisal methods.

Chapter One

Connections to Chén Lù's Ink Plum, the *Ringa-jō* (Album of Reproductions of Original Paintings), and the *Tan'yū Shukuzu*

As previously mentioned, several sketches in the *Baichiku Kashi Scroll* exhibit clear connections to existing works. Among them, four cases are particularly notable.

The first example is a plum painting on the 20th sheet of the upper row, annotated with the note: "*Received from Nakagawa Ritsusai; an outstanding piece*" (Fig. 1). This suggests that a scroll received from Nakagawa Ritsusai was highly esteemed. A comparison of the composition and inscription confirms that the original work referenced in this sketch is *Ink Plum Painting* by Chén Lù (陳錄), housed in the Tokyo National Museum (1446, TA-22, Ichikawa Beian Collection) (Fig. 2). Tan'yū carefully copied this piece while recognizing it as exceptional. Chén Lù, an artist active in 15th-century Ming Dynasty Kuàijī (modern-day Shaoxing, Zhejiang Province), was renowned for his ink plum paintings. This sketch provides insight into how his works were received in 17th-century Edo. Notably, Tan'yū did not mention the artist's name in his annotation, suggesting that he was unfamiliar with Chén Lù yet still judged the work as outstanding based solely on its style. This indicates that Tan'yū's appraisals were not necessarily influenced by an artist's fame.

The second case is a bamboo painting on the 21st sheet of the upper row, annotated: "*Received on the 22nd day of the 3rd month in 1668 from Rokugo Iga; said to be an authentic work of Dōngpō (東坡) (Sū Shì 蘇軾)*" (Fig. 3). The original work corresponding to this sketch is believed to be the silk ink painting housed in a private collection,⁵ which is also featured in the *Ringa-jō* (臨畫帖). The *Ringa-jō* is a two-volume album containing 100 reproductions of ancient paintings by Tan'yū, most of which are faithful copies with some modifications.⁶ Unlike the rapidly executed sketches in *Tan'yū Shukuzu*, the reproductions in the *Ringa-jō* were meticulously rendered. In both *Tan'yū Shukuzu* and the *Ringa-jō*, Tan'yū identified this bamboo painting as an authentic work of Sū Shì (1036–1101), one of the Four Great Masters of the Song Dynasty, even carefully transcribing the inscription.

Some of Tan'yū's reproductions bear his signature and were mounted as elaborate scrolls or albums, intended for appreciation despite being copies. Scholars such as Sumio Kageyama and Toshie Kihara⁷ have noted that Tan'yū frequently selected artists referenced in *Kundai Kan saucho-ki* (君台觀左右帳記) and *Kososhū* (後素集, compiled by Ikkei Kanō) for his reproductions, and Sū Shì was among them. This suggests that Tan'yū paid particular attention to this bamboo painting.

The owner of this painting, "Rokugo Iga dono," refers to Masakatsu Rokugo (1609–1677), the second lord of the Honjo domain. The Rokugo family, originally minor feudal lords of Rokugo-sho in Senboku, bore the surname Nikaido before it was changed to Rokugo by Masakatsu's grandfather, Michiyuki. According to the *Kansei Choshu Shokafu* (寛政重修諸家譜),⁸ Masakatsu first met Shogun Hidetada in 1615, succeeded his father's domain in 1634, and oversaw temple construction at Zojo-ji. In 1676, he retired and presented a Bizen Unju sword to the shogunate. The *Tokugawa Jikki* (徳川実紀, Tokugawa Chronicles) records that on July 11, 1674, "Rokugo Iga dono Masakatsu retired and presented a Unju sword."⁹ The *Shoke Ibutsu Tokumotsu Kenjouki* (諸家遺物得物献上記, Record of Family Heirlooms and Offerings) in the National Archives of Japan also documents that on July 11, Enpō 4 (1676), Masakatsu presented the Bizen Unju sword. His wife was the adopted daughter of Takamitsu Kyogoku, a high-ranking court official, further underscoring the Rokugo family's esteemed status, making them suitable patrons of a Sū Shì painting.

The third case involves a plum painting on the first sheet of the lower section, annotated: "*On the 13th day of the 8th month of 1668, it came from Uesugi Kiheiji-dono. Furthermore, in the copied version, it is inscribed as 'Ma Yuan' and is splendid.*" (Fig. 4). This painting corresponds to the ink plum painting in the 13th illustration of the lower volume of the *Ringa-jō*. Uesugi Kiheiji refers to Uesugi Tsunanori (1663–1704), the fourth lord of the Yonezawa domain, who was adopted into the Uesugi family after the sudden death of the third lord, Tsunakatsu. On July 11, 1664, he presented the heirlooms of his predecessor, Tsunakatsu, to the fourth shōgun Tokugawa Ietsuna, including the *Sakichisada* (佐吉貞) wakizashi and a hanging scroll of a cat by Emperor Huizong (徽宗).¹⁰ This is further corroborated by the previously mentioned *Records of Presentation of Heirlooms by Various Houses*, which states: "On the 11th day of the 7th month of Kanbun 4: Sakichisada wakizashi, valued at thirty gold pieces; hanging scroll of a cat by Emperor Huizong."¹¹ Additionally, Tsunanori had his first audience with the shōgun on the 25th day of the 8th month of Kanbun 8 (1668). It is particularly

noteworthy that the date recorded in the note, "13th day of the 8th month of Kanbun 8," falls just days before this significant event.

This "Plum and Moon" was evaluated as "splendid" by Tan'yū. The exact timing of its reproduction in the *Ringa-jō* is unclear, but it is possible that it was created around the same period. Notably, the note states, "In the copied version, it is inscribed as 'Mǎ Yuǎn.' Indeed, in the corresponding illustration in the '*Ringa-jō*,' there is also an inscription of 'Mǎ Yuǎn' (*kakitsuke*, a written notation on the painting), suggesting that the note refers to this particular illustration. This implies the possibility that the painting was appraised before Tsunanori's audience with the shōgun and that the appraisal and the creation of the reproduction were interconnected. In other words, the process of evaluating famous paintings and producing copied illustrations may have been considered as a continuous sequence. Additionally, It is significant that Tan'yū referred to such illustrations as *utsushi* (写し). He clearly used the term *utsushi* for these reproductions and *kakitsuke* (書付) for the directly written notations"

Next, *The Loquats* on the 66th sheet of the lower section is accompanied by a note stating: "On the 26th day of the first month of Kanbun 8, Ukon presented it. It came from Matsudaira Denzaemon and Shinjo Sōbe Echigo-dono. The outer title refers to Shùn jǔ. 'Regarding possession and future expectations, the title was to be replaced with an equivalent of five hundred kan (贖), but no conclusion was reached on the written notation, *kakitsuke*" (Fig. 5). The painting considered to share the same original as this piece is the 'Loquats' housed in the Freer Gallery of Art (Fig. 6) and the 34th illustration in the upper volume of the *Ringa-jō*. Both bear Tan'yū's *Seimei* seal and can be regarded as refined copies intended for appreciation, or *utsushi*. The note on the reduced-size version of the painting indicates that it was brought by *Ukon* (右近), referring to Kanō Tsunenobu (1636–1713), and that it belonged to the Shinjo family. Tan'yū admired the piece as a work of Shun ju (Qian Xuan) and wished to purchase it, offering a price of five hundred *kan*. Presumably, Tan'yū acquired *the Loquats* and went on to reproduction it at least twice. Thus, this loquat painting by Qian Xuan can be regarded as one that Tan'yū repeatedly depicted, highlighting the importance of multiple instances of *utsushi* production.

The four cases discussed above were paintings that Tan'yū appraised as "splendid" or "authentic." Notably, there are other examples in which paintings that Tan'yū evaluated as "splendid" or "authentic" in *Tan'yū Shukuzu* were also included in the *Ringa-jō*. One such case, as pointed out by Sakakibara Satoru,¹² is the 'Bamboo and

Rock Painting,' which has a note stating "It was conveyed as the authentic brushwork of Tán Zhīruì."

From this, it becomes evident that at least four paintings in the *Ringa-jō* were copies of high-quality works brought in for appraisal. The purpose of Tan'yū's *Tan'yū Syukuzu* was likely to serve his creative endeavors and simultaneously to function as materials for appraisal and the education of his disciples.¹³ Furthermore, it is now clear that appraisals directly led to the production of "*utsushi*." According to Kanō Einō's '*Honchō Gashi* (本朝画史),' in the Kyoto Kanō family, a "painting model" known as "The three volumes of our family's inherited sketchbooks" was passed down through generations. In the Edo Kanō school led by Tan'yū, his studies of ancient paintings—such as the '*Ringa-jō*' and other "*Ry ūsho*(流書)" and "*Hōsho*(倣書)" series—had a significant impact as painting models. These activities were undoubtedly underpinned by the daily practice of appraisal. Notably, some of the copied illustrations in the '*Ringa-jō*' also contain dates and other information, suggesting that they were not immediately intended as purely decorative *utsushi*.¹⁴ Mito Nobue conceptualizes these Kanō school painting albums as "*e-kagami* (絵鑑)" (picture albums) akin to ancient calligraphy albums, highlighting that "just as ancient calligraphy albums functioned as a means of collecting, appreciating, and appraising calligraphy, in painting as well, appraisal, collection, and appreciation were inseparable elements passed down together." Her further suggests that "various picture albums were created, depending on their position on the spectrum between appraisal and appreciation."

The resonance between the *Tan'yū Syukuzu* and the *Ringa-jō* observed above suggests that famous painting reproductions (*utsushi*) were created within the space between "appraisal and appreciation." This brings a new perspective on the *Tan'yū Syukuzu*. Next, we will examine the ownership details revealed through these annotations.

Chapter Two

The People in the *Baichiku Kashi* Scroll

The vast collection of reduced-scale drawings by Tan'yū was made possible by the steady influx of artworks brought to him for appraisal. Many of these works are now lost, and the individuals who commissioned Tan'yū's evaluations were often figures who have not attracted much historical attention. This chapter examines the names

recorded in the annotations of the Baichiku Kashi Scroll to explore the types of individuals who owned and sought appraisals of antique paintings in Edo-period culture. Most were daimyō or officials of the Tokugawa shogunate, and their names are listed in (Table 1).

Table 1

Paper Name	Notation	Person	Status, Rank, etc.
Upper Row, Paper 1	Kurihara Jin'emon	Kurihara Toshizane (~1684)	<i>Konando, Ōban</i>
Upper Row, Paper 2	Hachisuka <i>Hida-dono</i>	Hachisuka Takashige (1634–1707)	First Lord of Awa-Tomita Domain
Upper Row, Paper 3	Okabe <i>Shima-dono</i>	Okabe Naoyoshi (~1705)	<i>Koshō</i> (Page)
Upper Row, Paper 6	Takagi Sakuemon	Takagi Sakuemon (~1671)	Nagasaki Town Elder, Nagasaki Government Official
Upper Row, Paper 9	Gomi Tōkurō	Gomi Toyomune (~1680)	<i>Koshō</i> (Page)
Upper Row, Papers 15 & 72	Tsuchiya <i>Tajima-dono</i>	Tsuchiya Kazunao (1608–79)	First Lord of Tsuchiura Domain, <i>Rōjyu</i> (Senior Councilor)
Upper Row, Paper 21	Rokugo <i>Iga-dono</i>	Rokugo Masakatsu (1609–77)	2nd Lord of Honjō Domain
Upper Row, Papers 34 & 35	<i>Minoto-no</i>	Inaba Masanori (1623–96)	2nd Lord of Odawara Domain, <i>Taiseisanyo</i> (Senior Councilor)
Upper Row, Paper 36	Toki <i>Iyo-dono</i>	Toki Yoritsune (1641–1722)	<i>Koshōbangashira</i> (Page Captain), 2nd Lord of Ueyama Domain
Upper Row, Paper 37 / Lower Row, Paper 55	Matsudaira <i>Minbu-dono</i>	Matsudaira Ujinobu (1613–83)	<i>Shōinbangasira</i> (Guard Captain), <i>Ōban</i> (Great Guard), <i>Osobashū</i> (Shogun's Attendant)
Upper Row, Paper 41	Honda <i>Tosa-dono</i>	Honda Tadataka (1624–78)	<i>Koshō</i> (Page)
Upper Row, Paper 42	Asano <i>Uneme-dono</i>	Asano Nagatomo (1643–75)	2nd Lord of Akō Domain
Upper Row, Paper 48 / Lower Row, Paper 50	Kanamori <i>Hida-dono</i>	Kanamori Yoritsuna (1648–72)	5th Lord of Takayama Domain
Upper Row, Paper 52	Endo <i>Bizen-dono</i>	Endo Tsunetomo (1628–76)	3rd Lord of Yahata Domain

Lower Row, Papers 62 & 51	Mizuno <i>Dewa-dono</i>	Mizuno Tadamoto (1613–68)	2nd Lord of Matsumoto Domain, Osaka Castle Keeper
Upper Row, Paper 64	Chikudō	Hitomi Chikudō (1638–96)	Confucian Scholar
Upper Row, Paper 66	<i>Mito-dono</i>	Tokugawa Mitsukuni (1628– 1701)	2nd Lord of Mito Domain
Upper Row, Papers 67 & 68	Yōboku	Kanō Tsunenobu (1636– 1713)	Painter
Upper Row, Paper 71	Nagai <i>Hyūga-dono</i>	Nagai Naokiyo (1591–1671)	First Lord of Nagaoka Domain, First Lord of Takatsuki Domain
Upper Row, Paper 74	Kobori <i>Bitchu-dono</i>	Kobori Masayuki (1620–74)	2nd Lord of Komuro Domain, Enshū-style Tea Master
Upper Row, Paper 76	Hori <i>Hida-dono</i>	Hori Naoyoshi (1643–91)	2nd Lord of Kazusa-Kariya Domain, First Lord of Yahata Domain
Upper Row, Paper 82	Oda <i>Yamashiro-dono</i>	Oda Nagayori (1620–89)	3rd Lord of Uda-Matsuyama Domain
Upper Row, Papers 84 & 85	Hori <i>Mimasaka-dono</i>	Hori Chikamasa (1606–73)	2nd Lord of Karasuyama Domain, First Lord of Iida Domain
Lower Row, Paper 1	Uesugi <i>Kihēji-dono</i>	Uesugi Tsunanori (1633– 1704)	4th Lord of Yonezawa Domain
Lower Row, Paper 5	Takebe <i>Takumi-dono</i>	Takebe Masanaga (1603–72) (?)	First Lord of Hayashida Domain (?)
Lower Row, Papers 8 & 9	Nakane <i>Heishirō-dono</i>	Nakane Masayoshi (1657–92) (?)	<i>Shōinban</i> (The Shogun's Guard)(?)
Lower Row, Paper 42	Sano <i>Shuma-dono</i>	Sano Masachika (1618–89)	Government Accountant Head (Financial Magistrate)
Lower Row, Paper 49	Suzuki <i>Awaji-dono</i>	Suzuki Shigetaka (1615–76)	<i>Shōinban</i> (The Shogun's Guard), <i>Koshō</i> (Page), New Court Attendant
Lower Row, Paper 62	Naitō <i>Izumo-dono</i>	Naitō Tadakiyo (1621–90)	<i>Koshō</i> (Page), Shogun's Close Aide
Lower Row, Paper 68	Miura <i>Shima-dono</i>	Miura Yasutsugu (1633–82)	2nd Lord of Mibu Domain, 2nd Lord of Katsuyama Domain

Upper Row, Sheet 1

The first sheet of the upper row contains the annotation: *"On the 27th, from Kurihara Jin'emon, mentioned that the artist is unknown."* (Fig. 7). Kurihara Jin'emon refers to Kurihara Toshizane (~1684),¹⁵ whose name frequently appears in the *Tan'yū Shukuzu* collection. He inherited his father's position in 1642 and became an *konando*(小納戸), a official responsible for managing the shogun's personal affairs. In 1654, he was reassigned to the *Ōban* (大番), the standing army of the shogunate. The Kurihara family had a long history of serving as *konando*, overseeing the management of the shogun's furnishings, tribute goods, and gifts.

Upper Row, Sheet 2

The second sheet bears a note by Tan'yū stating: *"On October 7, 1666, from Hachisuka Hida-dono, an authentic Sesshū (雪舟) work valued at three gold pieces."* (Fig. 8). Tan'yū authenticated this painting as an original work by Sesshū and appraised its value at three gold pieces. Hachisuka Hida-dono refers to Hachisuka Takashige (1634–1707), the first lord of the Awa Tomita Domain. In 1644, he became a page (*kosho*, 小姓) to Tokugawa Ietsuna and had an audience with Shogun Iemitsu in the same year. In 1657, he was promoted to a high-ranking official and received a stipend of 3,000 *koku*. In 1666, he was assigned to assist Hachisuka Tsunamichi, the lord of the Tokushima Domain, and later supported Hachisuka Tsunanori in 1678. He retired in 1706, presenting a Bizen Masamitsu (備前政光) sword to Shogun Ienobu.¹⁶

Upper Row, Sheet 3

The third sheet states: *"On May 14, 1666, from Okabe Shima-dono, stating that the artist is unknown and often counterfeit."* (Fig. 9). Okabe Shima-dono refers to Okabe Naoyoshi (d.1705),¹⁷ who had his first audience with Shogun Ietsuna in 1654 and became a page (*kosho*) in 1656. His painting of plum blossoms and snow was appraised as "a frequently seen counterfeit."

Upper Row, Sheet 6

The sixth sheet is annotated: *"On April 21, 1662, from Takagi Sakuemon, determined to be an inferior Chinese painting."* (Fig. 10). Takagi Sakuemon (d.1671) was a Nagasaki town elder, a position inherited through generations.¹⁸ The third Sakuemon took office in 1662, overseeing the shogunate's purchases in Nagasaki trade. It has been noted that

Tan'yū had connections with the Dutch trading post,¹⁹ and Takagi Sakuemon's name appears multiple times in *Tan'yū Shukuzu*.²⁰ This suggests that he frequently sought Tan'yū's appraisals. His association with Inaba Masanori, a known patron of Tan'yū, may have influenced this connection.

Upper Row, Sheet 9

The ninth sheet states: "*On March 20, 1671, Gomi Tōkurō's retainer Miyabe Nao'emon brought this piece, which was ordered by the Kyoto magistrate.*" (Fig. 11). Gomi Tōkurō refers to Gomi Toyomune (~1680),²¹ who had his first audience with Shogun Iemitsu in 1645 and became a page (kosho) the following year. After his brother's death in 1663, he inherited his father's position and was appointed Kyoto magistrate in 1664. The note indicates that Miyabe Nao'emon was sent from the Kyoto magistrate's office. Tan'yū identified the painting as a work of Chéng Nányún (程南雲), a Ming-dynasty calligrapher known for painting snow-covered plum trees and bamboo.²²

Upper Row, Sheet 15

The fifteenth sheet contains the note: "*On May 23, from Tsuchiya Tajima-dono, stating that the artist of this medieval painting is unknown.*" (Fig. 12). Tsuchiya Tajima-dono refers to Tsuchiya Kazunao (1608–1679), the first lord of the Tsuchiura Domain.²³ He had an audience with Shogun Hidetada in 1616 and later served as an attendant to Shogun Iemitsu. In 1662, he was appointed senior councilor (wakadoshiyori, 若年寄) and was later promoted to chief councilor (rōjū, 老中) in 1665, playing a significant role in Tokugawa Ietsuna's administration. His name also appears on the seventy-second sheet (Fig. 13), where a painting is attributed to Oguri Sōtan (小栗宗湛).

Upper Row, Sheets 34–35

These sheets bear the inscription: "*Received from Minodono on the 27th.*" (Fig. 14). "Minodono" refers to Inaba Mino-no-Kami, or Inaba Masanori (1623–1696).²⁴ Masanori was the legitimate grandson of Kasuga no Tsubone (春日局). In 1629, he had an audience with Shogun Hidetada, and in 1634, he inherited his father's domain. He rose to prominence in 1657 when he was appointed senior councilor (rōjū, 老中), and in 1680, he became Grand Advisor (taiseisanyō, 大政参与). Masanori was also responsible for managing trade with the Dutch Trading Post on behalf of the shogunate and had extensive knowledge of Dutch culture. In his later years, he became a significant patron

of Tan'yū.²⁵ This illustration does not include any dates or personal evaluations but faithfully reproduces the signature and inscription of "Baidōjin", referring to Wu Zhen (1280–1354), one of the Four Great Masters of the late Yuan dynasty, known for his landscapes, ink plum, and ink bamboo paintings.

Upper Row, Sheet 36

This sheet states: *"On February 11, received from Toki Iyo-dono. Delivered from the Library Department. It was attributed to Chūshō, identified as a work by Tōba, but later refuted as not being a Tōba work. The Library Department confirmed this."* (Fig. 15). Toki Iyo-dono refers to Toki Yorishige (1641–1722), the second lord of the Kaminoyama Domain.²⁶ In 1652, he had an audience with Shogun Ietsuna, and in 1663, he joined the Shoinban (書院番, an elite guard unit). He later became a page in 1665 and was given the title of Iyo-dono. In 1672, he was promoted to head of the page corps. Although the exact year of this reduced-scale drawing is unclear, it must have been after 1665, and it is evident that the Library Department acted as the intermediary.

Upper Row, Sheet 37

The note on this sheet reads: *"On February 4, Enpō 2 (1674), received from Matsudaira Minbu-dono. A medieval painting, artist unknown."* (Fig. 16). Matsudaira Minbu-dono refers to Matsudaira Ujinobu (1613–1683).²⁷ He had an audience with Shogun Iemitsu in 1625 and initially served as the Shogun's meal attendant in the Inner Chambers. He later became captain of the Shoinban, then a senior retainer in the Western Palace, and eventually head of the Shoinban, Ōbangashira, and a close advisor (osobashū, 御側衆) to Shogun Ietsuna. This illustration was labeled "fudesirazu" (筆知らず, unknown artist).

Upper Row, Sheet 41

This sheet states: *"From Honda Tosa-dono, two scrolls of bamboo and trees were found wanting in quality, and thus no purchase was deemed requisite. The estimated price was set at 150 kan."* (Fig. 17). Honda Tosa-dono refers to Honda Tadataka (1625–1678).²⁸ In 1641, he had an audience with Shogun Iemitsu and became a page to Ietsuna on October 3 of the same year. The note indicates that the two scrolls were of poor quality, and their purchase was deemed unnecessary, with an estimated price of 150 kan.

Upper Row, Sheet 42

This sheet states: *"On August 13, received from Asano Uneme-dono. The artist's signature is unclear, but it was stated to be an authentic work."* (Fig. 18). Asano Uneme-dono refers to Asano Nagatomo (1643–1675), the second lord of the Akō Domain.²⁹ He inherited the domain in 1671 following his father's retirement but passed away in 1675 at the age of 33. His eldest son, Asano Naganori (1667–1701), later inherited the domain and became known for his role in the Akō Incident. The note includes the signature of "Baika Dōjin", confirming this as a work by Wu Zhen. Interestingly, Tan'yū noted uncertainty regarding its authenticity, stating: *"I do not know whether it is an authentic work of Baika Dōjin, but it has been deemed as such."* This suggests that Tan'yū's written evaluations in the *Tan'yū Shukuzu* sometimes differed from official appraisals, highlighting their private nature.³⁰

Upper Row, Sheet 48

The inscription on this sheet reads: *"Kanbun 11 (1671), March 11, inscribed by Kin Setsugan. Came from Kanamori Hida-dono. It is said to be his own painting."* (Fig. 19). Kanamori Hida-dono refers to Kanamori Yoritsugu (1648–1672), the fifth lord of the Takayama Domain.³¹ He had an audience with Shogun Ietsuna in 1659 and inherited his father's domain in 1665. He passed away at the age of 24 in December 1672, the year of this appraisal. The phrases "inscribed by Kin Setsugan" and "said to be his own painting" indicate that Tan'yū appraised this as an inscribed self-painting by Setsugan (possibly Sōkin).

Upper Row, Sheet 52

The fifty-second sheet in the upper row contains the following inscription: *"Same year, October 19, from Endō Bizen. A painting from the Middle Ages, the artist is unknown. It is of the level of Baidōjin (梅道人)."* (Fig. 20). Endō Bizen-dono refers to Endō Tsunetomo (1628–1676), the third lord of the Gujō Hachiman Domain and the Osaka Castle commander.³² His ancestor, Tō no Tsuneyori (?-?), is recognized as the founder of the Kokin Transmission (古今伝授), a lineage of poetic scholarship. Tsunetomo is particularly known for compiling the Tsuneyori-shū, a poetry anthology completed by imperial command of Emperor Go-Mizunoo. In this instance, Tan'yū identified the painting as an old Chinese work by an unknown artist but speculated that it might be from Wu Zhen or an artist of similar caliber.

Upper Row, Sheet 62

The inscription on this sheet reads: "*Kanbun 6 (1666), September 22, from Mizuno Dewa-dono. Boke nasubi, attributed to Sesshū.*" (Fig. 21). Mizuno Dewa-no-dono refers to Mizuno Tadatoshi (1613–1668), lord of the Matsumoto Domain.³³ His grandfather, Mizuno Tadashige (1541–1600), was recognized as one of Tokugawa's Twenty Great Generals. In 1652, Mizuno Tadatoshi was appointed Osaka Castle commander. At the time, Tan'yū appraised the *Mokke Nasubi* painting, attributing it to Sesshū, and inscribed an authentication title (*kiwamegaki*, 極め書き) to validate its attribution.

Upper Row, Sheet 64

The sixty-fourth sheet in the upper row contains the following note: "*On February 3rd, a letter of appreciation was sent from Tatsube Jitoku. The painting is by Sōami.*" (Fig. 22). This suggests that both Hitomi Chikudō and Tan'yū collaborated in inscribing an appreciation text, which has been preserved. From this, it can be inferred that Chikudō, alongside Tatsube Jitoku, composed a commendatory text for a painting attributed to Sōami, which was in Jitoku's possession. Hitomi Chikudō (1638–1696) was the second son of Hitomi Gentoku, a shogunate physician.³⁴ He studied under Hayashi Razan and Hayashi Gahō, later becoming a Confucian scholar for the shogunate in the first year of the Kanbun era (1661). He also participated in the compilation of *Honchō Tsugan*. Chikudō maintained close friendships with Tan'yū and his nephew Jōshin, and he contributed a colophon to the *Hōko Zukan* (Illustrated Scroll of Ancient Imitations), which was specially commissioned by Inaba Masanori from Tan'yū.

Upper Row, Sheet 66

The sixty-sixth sheet contains the note: "*On the second day of the fifth month of 1669, an old painting from the Mito household was examined, and it was suggested that it could also be by this hand. It was owned by a person named Yokota Saemon.*" (Fig. 23).

This entry also transcribes the signature on the painting, "Huang Jucai hua", indicating that the work was attributed to Huang Jucai (933–?), a Northern Song painter and the son of Huang Quan (c. 903–965). Few of his works survive, but he was renowned for his meticulous brushwork, rich coloration (*gōraku nōsai*), and depictions of flowers, bamboo, and small birds. While the sketch does not fully capture his artistic style, Tan'yū regarded this flower-and-insect painting as a possible work by Huang

Jucai. The identity of Yokota Saemon remains unclear, though he may have been a retainer of the Mito household.

Upper Row, Sheets 67–68

The sixty-seventh and sixty-eighth sheets contain the following notes: "*On the 26th of the same ninth month, brought from Yōboku's place, bearing the Kohogen (古法眼) seal, said to be an authentic brushwork.*"

"*On the last day of the same eleventh month, from Yōboku's place, bearing the seal, said to be a brushwork of Kohogen.*" (Fig. 24). Yōboku refers to Kanō Tsuneshige (1636–1713), Tan'yū's nephew, who took the artist name "Yōboku" and was also known as Ukon. Both illustrations depict chestnuts and bear the "Kohogen" seal, which refers to Kanō Motonobu (1476–1559). It is likely that these old paintings were first brought to Tsuneshige for evaluation, and he then sought Tan'yū's expert opinion for authentication. Similar notations such as "brought from Yōboku's place" or "brought from Ukon's place" frequently appear in the *Tan'yū shukuzu*,³⁵ suggesting that Tsuneshige regularly consulted Tan'yū on matters of attribution.

Upper Row, Sheet 71

The seventy-first sheet includes the following note: "*On the fifth day of the same tenth month, from Nagai Hyūga-dono, titled 'Shunju'.*" (Fig. 25). Nagai Hyūga-dono refers to Nagai Naokiyo (1591–1671), who was the lord of the Nagaoka Domain in Yamashiro Province and later became the lord of the Takatsuki Domain.³⁶ He served Shogun Tokugawa Hidetada as a page and later as a member of the shoin-ban guard. His elder brother, Nagai Naomasa (1587–1668), was a prominent daimyō and tea master. Together, they governed Kyoto and played roles in the construction of the Imperial Palace and Osaka Castle.

The pomegranate painting mentioned in the note was authenticated as a work by Shùn jǔ, the courtesy name of Qian Xuan (birth and death unknown), also known by the art names Yutan and Xunfeng. He was a scholar-official of the Southern Song dynasty and was skilled in figure painting, landscapes, and flora and fauna, excelling in the "cut-branch" painting style. As noted earlier, Tan'yū repeatedly painted loquat trees in the style of Qian Xuan, demonstrating his admiration for the artist's technique.

Upper Row, Sheet 74

The seventy-fourth sheet states: *"On the 27th of the same ninth month, brought from Lord Kobori Bitchū, considered possibly to be the work of Zhao Chang, but determined as 'brushwork unknown'."* (Fig. 26). Kobori Bitchū-dono refers to Kobori Masayuki (1620–1674), the second lord of the Komuro Domain and second son of Kobori Enshū (1579–1647).³⁷ Masayuki studied calligraphy under Shōkadō Shōjō and was a cultural figure instrumental in the development of the Enshū school of tea ceremony.

The painting was suspected to be the work of Zhao Chang (birth and death unknown), who was also known by the courtesy name Changzhi and was a native of Guanghan (Sichuan). He was particularly known for his vibrant and skillful depictions of flowers, fruits, and cut-branch compositions, which were highly praised for their exquisite use of color. However, Tan'yū ultimately determined that the brushwork was unknown.

Upper Row, Sheet 76

The seventy-sixth sheet contains the note: *"On the 2nd of the same fourth month, brought from Lord Hori Hida-dono, a large medieval Chinese painting, splendid in appearance (...) to be officially appraised."* (Fig. 27). Hori Hida-dono refers to Hori Naoyoshi (1643–1691), the second lord of the Kariya Domain and the first lord of the Hachiman Domain.³⁸ He inherited his domain in 1668 following his father Hori Naokage's retirement and later served as an Osaka Castle magistrate. The note indicates that this was a large-scale Chinese painting of exceptional quality and that a formal appraisal was necessary.

Upper Row, Sheet 82

The eighty-second sheet states: *"Kinshō: An imperial-themed pine painting, on the same day, brought from Lord Oda Yamashiro, identified as a copy of Nichikan."* (Fig. 28). Oda Yamashiro-dono refers to Oda Nagayori (1620–1689),³⁹ born in Kaga as the second son of Oda Takanaga. His father had served the Maeda family, but when his grandfather Oda Nobuo passed away in 1630, Takanaga succeeded the Uda-Matsuyama Domain and became a daimyō.

A grape painting owned by Nagayori was authenticated by Tan'yū as an "utsushi-mono" (copy) of Nichikan. Nichikan (birth and death unknown) was a Buddhist monk-

painter active during the late Southern Song to early Yuan dynasty, best known for his grape paintings. Many such works were likely transmitted to Japan during this period. Another painting with the same composition appears on the 82nd sheet of the lower row, but it was identified as a counterfeit. This suggests that many forgeries of such works were in circulation at the time.⁴⁰

Upper Row, Sheets 84–85

The eighty-fourth and eighty-fifth sheets contain the following note: "*On the 26th of the ninth month of Kanbun 1, brought from Lord Hori Mimasaka, determined as an authentic brushwork.*" (Fig. 29). Hori Mimasaka-dono refers to Hori Chikamasa (1606–1673), the second lord of the Karasuyama Domain and the first lord of the Iida Domain.⁴¹ He inherited the domain following the death of his father in Kan'ei 14 (1637). His wife, Jōshin-in, was the daughter of Sanjōnishi Sanetsura, a prominent court noble.

Lower Row, Sheet 5

The fifth sheet of the lower row includes the following note: "*On the 5th of the sixth month of Kanbun 3, brought from Lord Takebe Takumi, a painting is a counterfeit used item.*" (Fig. 30). Takebe Takumi is believed to refer to Takebe Masanaga (1603–1672), the first lord of the Hayashida Domain.⁴² However, Masanaga was appointed as Tanba-dono in Kanbun 1, while his fifth son, Masahiro, was appointed as Takumi-dono in Kanbun 9. Given that the note refers to "Takumi-dono" in Kanbun 3, it is likely referring to Masanaga himself. Masanaga inherited the Takebe family's domain at the age of eight and, with the support of his maternal grandfather, Ikeda Terumasa, distinguished himself. Upon his retirement in Kanbun 7, he presented a painting of Hanshan and Shide by Yan Hui to the shogunate. The *Shokei Ibutsu Tokumotsu Kenjō-ki* records this as: "*A painting by Yan Hui of Hanshan and Shide, owned by Takebe Tanba-dono.*"

Lower Row, Sheets 8–9

The eighth and ninth sheets of the lower row contain the following note: "*On the 20th of the fifth month of Kanbun 6, concerning Nakane Heishirō, written by Ranshōrō, a large-scale painting / Identified as the work of Wang Yuanzhang (with red and white square seals).*" (Fig. 31). Nakane Heishirō is believed to be Nakane

Masayoshi (d. 1692).⁴³ He had an audience with the shogun at the age of eleven in Kanbun 7, later became a member of the shoin-ban guard in Enpō 6, and passed away at the age of thirty-six in Genroku 5, predeceasing his father. His father, Nakane Masanori, and grandfather, Nakane Masamori, were also retainers of the shogunate. The painting in question was authenticated as an ink plum painting by Wang Yuanzhang, also known as Wang Mian (1310–1359). Wang Mian was a late Yuan-period painter and poet, known for his paintings of plum blossoms, which had a significant influence on Japanese artists.

Lower Row, Sheet 42

The forty-second sheet includes the following note:

"On the 18th of the same twelfth month, brought from Lord Sano Shume, said to be 'Chūshō,' possibly an authentic work, but appraised at one silver piece (...). The price is considered low." (Fig. 32). Sano Shume refers to Sano Masachika (1618–1690), who served as kanjyōkumigashira (head of the accounting department).⁴⁴ He became an accounting apprentice in 1637 and was promoted to accounting officer in 1645. In 1658, he was appointed as an official overseeing the recasting of gold coins after the Great Meireki Fire and later participated in the reconstruction of the Imperial Palace in 1665. It is particularly noteworthy that the appraisal value was explicitly recorded as "one silver piece," suggesting that the painting was not considered highly valuable despite being potentially authentic. It is interesting that the low appraisal given to the painting owned by Sano, who was the shogunate's financial officer, was deliberately emphasized in the record.

Lower Row, Sheet 49

The forty-ninth sheet contains the following note:

"On the 7th of the ninth month of Kanbun 9, brought from Lord Suzuki Awaji, authorship unknown, but possibly a self-painted work." (Fig. 33). Suzuki Awaji-dono refers to Suzuki Shigetaka (d. 1676).⁴⁵ He served Shogun Tokugawa Hidetada as a member of the shoin-ban guard before transferring to the kosho-gumi (small page unit). In 1663, he was appointed Awaji-dono with the Junior Fifth Rank, Lower Grade. He passed away in 1676 at the age of sixty-two. As a hatamoto (direct retainer of the shogun), he served three shoguns: Hidetada, Iemitsu, and Ietsuna. This painting includes an inscription reading: "Night rain ..., cold green, in front of the seat, Shengshi." Based

on this, it was appraised as possibly being a self-inscribed work by an artist named Shengshi. However, the identity of this artist remains unknown.

Lower Row, Sheet 51

The fifty-first sheet of the lower row contains the following note: *"Lord Mizuno Yama brought a hanging scroll, titled Jingcheng, with the signature 'Jingcheng Han Xu' copied in the painting."* (Fig. 34). There are only a few known examples of works by Han Xu (韓旭), one of which is Algae and Fish, currently housed at the Nezu Museum in Tokyo. Therefore, this sketch serves as a rare historical record of Han Xu's works. "Mizuno Dewa-dono" refers to Mizuno Tadatoshi,⁴⁶ the second lord of the Matsumoto Domain. He supervised the construction of stone walls at Edo Castle and served three terms as the Osaka-jōdai (Osaka Castle Magistrate): Shōō 1 (1652), Manji 1 (1658), Kanbun 1 (1661).

Lower Row, Sheet 55

The fifty-fifth sheet includes the following note: *"On the 13th of the same eleventh month, brought from Lord Matsudaira Minbu, identified as a work by Sōami, appraised within two gold pieces."* (Fig. 35). Lord Matsudaira Minbu refers to Matsudaira Ujinobu, who was previously mentioned on the thirty-seventh sheet of the upper row. The painting, depicting Squashes, was attributed to Sōami and appraised at a value of two gold pieces.

Lower Row, Sheet 61

The sixty-first sheet contains the following note: *"On the 5th of the same tenth month, among a set of three hanging scrolls, the central painting is a Daruma painting attributed to Kofogen, but the authorship of both side paintings is unknown. Lord Naitō Izumo."* (Fig. 36). Naitō Izumo-dono refers to Naitō Tadayasu (d. 1690).⁴⁷ He had an audience with Shogun Tokugawa Iemitsu in 1630 and later became a kosho (page) to Shogun Ietsuna in 1641. He received the title Izumo-dono in 1645 and was later promoted to a close attendant of the shogun in 1653, serving alongside: Kuze Hiroyuki, Makino Chikanari, Tsuchiya Kazunao (previously mentioned in the scroll). However, in 1661, he fell out of favor and was temporarily exiled due to an offense, though he was later pardoned and reinstated as a yoriki (retainer). This record describes a set of three

hanging scrolls, where the central piece was attributed to Kofogen (Kanō Motonobu) and depicted Daruma. The authorship of the two side scrolls remains unknown.

Lower Row, Sheet 69

The sixty-ninth sheet includes the following note: "*Sokuan Nichiyo, on the 29th of the second month of Kanbun 6, brought from Lord Miura Shima, identified as a work of Sesson, but authenticity unknown.*" (Fig. 37). The presence of the inscription "Sokuan Nichiyo" suggests that the original painting referenced in this sketch is the Turnip and Radish painting attributed to Muqi, currently housed in the Sannomaru Shōzōkan (Museum of the Imperial Household).⁴⁸ The note states "identified as a work of Sesson," yet paintings by Sesson based on Muqi's *Turnip and Radish* are preserved at the Institute for Zen Studies. However, this particular sketch does not match any existing Sesson works.

In this case, a painting brought by Miura Shima-dono was submitted for authentication under the assumption that it was by Sesson, but the response indicated that its authenticity remained uncertain. The owner, Miura Shima-dono, refers to Miura Yasutsugu,⁴⁹ the second lord of the Mibu Domain in Shimotsuke Province. He later became the second head of the Miura family in the Katsuyama Domain of Mimasaka Province.

The above is an overview of the contents identified from the names mentioned in the annotations of the *Baichiku Kashi Scroll*. Most of the individuals were retainers of the shogunate, but some were also local officials and scholars. Next, we will discuss the significance of the information conveyed through these paintings owned and associated with such individuals. Next, we will examine the historical and cultural significance of these paintings in relation to their ownership and the individuals who possessed them.

Chapter Three

Characteristics and Significance of the *Baichiku Kashi Scroll*

As discussed, the *Baichiku Kashi Scroll* contains numerous appraisals of Chinese paintings, making it a valuable historical record of Edo-period art evaluation, particularly in relation to Chinese paintings. Additionally, it reveals how artists such as Kanō Motonobu (1476–1559) and Sesson (1492–1589) studied and reproduced Chinese paintings, which later became independent works recognized under their own names.

One notable example is the variation of the attributed Muqi painting found on the sixty-eighth sheet. Today, similar paintings attributed to Sesson exist, such as those preserved at the Zen Culture Research Institute.⁵⁰ From the *Tan'yū Shukuzu*, we can trace a lineage of variations in depictions of *Radish and Turnip* (蘿蔔蕪菁図) by artists working within the Chinese painting tradition, with the attributed Muqi painting (伝牧谿図) as the starting point.

According to the historical records accompanying the *Radish and Turnip* painting housed in the Museum of the Imperial Collections, Sannomaru Shōzōkan, this work was said to have been owned by the Mito family during Tan'yū's time.⁵¹ If that is the case, then this painting was likely a well-known masterpiece that Tan'yū was familiar with. Rather than ignoring its existence, Tan'yū explicitly distinguished his version as an "utsushi"

Furthermore, a clear distinction was made between "utsushi" (study copies or reproductions for appreciation) and "utsushimono" (forgeries). The "utsushi" by Sesson and Motonobu were likely regarded as independent works possessing both technical excellence and artistic value. The *Tan'yū Shukuzu* conveys how such masterpieces were copied and widely appreciated, demonstrating Tan'yū's awareness of famous Chinese paintings and his ability to distinguish between authentic reproductions and outright forgeries.

Tan'yū's Aesthetic Judgment and Critical Evaluations are particularly evident in his assessments of certain paintings. One notable example of his artistic sensibility appears on the fifty-seventh sheet, which states: "*On May 21, Yang Yuan was assigned as the title based on the guardian's statement; the painting is irksome, but the title matches.*" (Fig. 38).

This note refers to Tan'yū's evaluation of a painting owned by Heki Iemon, which he attributed to Yang Yuan (楊瑗). The term "irksome" (*iradatashii mono*) reveals Tan'yū's subjective aesthetic judgment, making this entry significant in understanding his artistic preferences and critical evaluations.

A painting attributed to Yang Yuan, titled *Vegetable Painting*, is held in the Sendai City Museum,⁵² and its unique style may have contributed to Tan'yū's critical response. This case highlights the diversity of Tan'yū's appraisals, where not all attributed works were valued positively.

Furthermore, variations can be observed in Tan'yū's brushwork and coloring techniques, depending on the subject matter. Notably, paintings deemed "remarkable" in the appraisal process are rendered with exceptional care.

For example, on the seventy-eighth sheet of the upper row, an entry states: "*On the 24th day of the 10th month of 1662, Sōken presented this painting. It is said to be an ancient Chinese painting. The brushwork is not a mere copy. It is a grand and remarkable painting.*" (Fig. 39).

This sketch is meticulously executed, with delicate brushstrokes and enhanced with subtle coloration. Tan'yū did not consider this painting of confectionery to be a mere copy, but rather an authentic and distinguished work, praising it as "grand and remarkable".

The *Baichiku Kashi Scroll* serves as an important historical document that not only provides insight into Edo-period art appraisals but also highlights the distinctions made between copies, reproductions, and forgeries. Through this collection, Tan'yū's deep knowledge of Chinese painting traditions, critical evaluations, and artistic sensibilities become evident.

Moreover, his ability to recognize the artistic value of "utsushi" while differentiating them from "utsushimono" reflects the intellectual rigor applied in the Kanō school's study of past masters. The scroll illustrates how famous works were copied, interpreted, and appreciated within Edo-period artistic culture, reinforcing the significance of art appraisal as both a scholarly and creative endeavor.

Conclusion

The extensive documentation of paintings, seals, inscriptions, and annotations in Tan'yū's *reduced-scale drawings* remains an invaluable resource for art historical research. The *Baichiku Kashi Scroll* alone provides a wealth of information, offering critical insights into the reception and appreciation of Chinese paintings in early Edo-period Japan.

With the increasing digitalization of Edo-period reproductions, online accessibility has improved. However, many of the most significant insights emerge only through meticulous examination of annotations and inscriptions. This study has underscored

Tan'yū's role as a connoisseur, highlighting his critical judgments and personal reflections on the artworks he appraised.

Few painters in East Asian art history have left behind such comprehensive appraisal records, making further research into Tan'yū's documentation essential for a deeper understanding of his artistic vision and influence. Continued investigation of these historical records remains a vital academic pursuit, shedding light on the artistic networks, methodologies, and evaluative criteria of the Edo period.

Notes

- ¹ The major "*Tan'yū Shukuzu*" (Tan'yū Reduced Drawings) that have been published or made available on the internet include the following (references in parentheses):
- Ibaraki Prefectural Museum of History Collection ("Special Exhibition: Muromachi Ink Paintings and Early Modern Paintings," Ibaraki Prefectural Museum of History, 1983)
 - MOA Museum of Art Collection (Motoaki Kono, "Creation of an Index for Tan'yū Shukuzu," Annual Report of the Kashima Art Foundation, Vol. 5, 1987)
 - Okura Shukokan Collection ("Tan'yū Shukuzu in the Okura Shukokan Collection," Okura Cultural Foundation, 1981; Motoyuki Okura, "Tan'yū Shukuzu: On the Reduced Drawings in the Okura Shukokan Collection," *Kokka*, No. 60, 1981)
 - Kyoto National Museum Collection (Edited by Kyoto National Museum, "Tan'yū Shukuzu," Vols. 1 and 2, Dōbōsha Publishing, 1981)
 - Jissen Women's University Collection (Noriko Miyazaki, "Tan'yū Shukuzu in the Jissen Women's University Library Collection," *Jissen Women's University Aesthetics and Art History*, No. 25, 2011)
 - Shōdenji Temple Collection (Yuya Fukushi, "A Newly Discovered Tan'yū Shukuzu: A Study on 'Fierce Tiger' (Shōdenji Temple) Attributed to Li Gonglin," *Kokka*, No. 1434, 2015)
 - Seijo University Collection (Available on the digital archive 'Precious Materials' of the Seijo University Library website)
 - British Museum Collection ("Secret Japanese Art Collection," Vol. 2, Kodansha, 1992)
 - Tenri University Collection (Kensuke Chikamoto, "Annotated Reproduction of the Illustrated Scroll Reproductions of Tan'yū Shukuzu in the Tenri Library Collection: 'Gedan Shōnin Myōe Shōnin Den Emaki' and 'Tengu Sōshi'," *Yamabe Road*, No. 42, 1998)

- Tokyo University of the Arts Collection (Motoaki Kono, "Introduction to 'Tan'yū Shukuzu' in the Tokyo University of the Arts Museum Collection," *Bijutsushi Ronso*, No. 9, 1993)
- Tokyo National Museum Collection (Mayumi Ono, "Newly Acquired Works: Tan'yū Shukuzu by Kanō Tan'yū," *MUSEUM*, Nos. 598 & 601, 2005-2006)
- University of Tokyo Collection ("Tokyo University Collection I: The Formative World of East Asia," University of Tokyo General Research Museum, 1994)
- Nara National Museum Collection ("Introduction of Newly Acquired Items," *Bulletin of Nara National Museum 'Rokuen Zasshū'*, No. 8, 2006)
- Berlin Museum of Asian Art Collection (Bettina Klein, translated by Kaoru Kojima, "Shukuzu Album 'Hitsuen Itsuyū' in the Berlin Museum of Asian Art Collection," *Kokka*, No. 1091, 1986; "Secret Japanese Art Collection," Vol. 7, Kodansha, 1992)
- Yamato Bunkakan Collection ("35th Anniversary Special Exhibition: Diptychs - Masterpieces of Chinese Painting," Yamato Bunkakan, 1995)
- Private Collections (Bunjinga Institute, "Tan'yū Shukuzu," Yabumoto Sogorō, 1986)
- Private Collections (Tadashi Kobayashi, "Edo Masterpiece Painting Album Collection," Vol. IV Kano school, Shinshindosyupan, 1994)

It should be noted that this paper does not include Tan'yū's *shinkeizu* (true-view paintings) (held by the Gotoh Museum, Dai-Tokyu Memorial Library, and private collections) or his botanical sketches (held by the Tokyo National Museum and Kyoto National Museum) in its examination of Tan'yū Shukuzu.

- ² In addition to this work, the Tokyo National Museum houses a single volume of "Tan'yū Shukuzu Scroll" (A-1370), two volumes of "Tan'yū Shukuzu Scroll" (A-1382), and eighteen albums of "Tan'yū Shukuzu" (A-12301).
- ³ Several cut marks are visible, suggesting that the work was trimmed for some reason after it had been arranged into a format closer to its present condition. The cut marks are indicated in Source 1 as "cut marks present."
- ⁴ The *Koga Biko* contains an inscription on Tan'yū Shukuzu by Hiyama Tansai, who notes: "This small abridged version, originating from the house of Tan'yū Hōin, has been widely dispersed in society. Whenever I see these small sketches, I am moved by Tan'yū-sai's earnest spirit. Although hastily drawn, they are worth viewing. However, one particular doubt arises: the sketches that include the inscriptions 'Hōin approved' or 'Hōgan approved' may in fact be copies by Kanō Tanenobu Morimasa (1653–1718)." This suggests that later descendants also created shukuzu copies, a fact that must be taken into account. (*Koga Biko*, revised and annotated by Asaoka Kōtei and Ota Kinzo, vol. 2, Yoshikawakobunkan, 1904, p. 1640). Furthermore, the same book records that during the era of Kanō Tanpoku (1762–1832), the ancient paintings

collected by Tan'yū were scattered. The remaining sketchbooks, antiques, and old paintings were lost in the Great Fire of Bunka during the time of Kanō Tanenobu Morimichi (1785–1836). Additionally, Kadowaki Mutsumi states that the Tan'yū Shukuzu were also dispersed along with these old paintings in Tanpoku's era (Kadowaki Mutsumi, *The Birth of the Great Master Kanō Tan'yū: The Talent and Circumstances of the Edo-Period Painter Beloved by Shoguns and Emperors*, Asahi Shimbun Publications, 2014, pp. 124–132). However, based on the colophons in this study, no shukuzu by artists other than Tan'yū were identified in the "Baichiku Kashi Scroll." Nonetheless, for shukuzu without colophons, it is difficult to attribute them to specific artists based solely on style and handwriting.

- ⁵ Regarding the *Ringa-jō*, refer to Note 1: *Tan'yū Shukuzu* edited by the Literati Painting Research Institute, and *Edo Master Painting Album IV: Kanō School – Tan'yū, Morikage, and Itchō*, edited by Kobayashi Tadashi, Shinshindō Publishing, 1994.
- ⁶ Nobue Mito, "The Art Museum on the Desk: The World of *Tegami* and *Gachō*," in *Masterpieces of Kohitsu Tegami and Gachō: Art Albums of Early Modern Japan*, Suntory Museum of Art, 2001, pp. 120–123; Sakakibara Satoru, *Kanō Tan'yū: Portrait of an Official Painter*, Rinsen Bookstore, 2014, pp. 613–625.
- ⁷ Kageyama Sumio, "Kanō Tan'yū's *Homage to Ancient Paintings Scroll*," *MUSEUM* 410, 1985, p. 19; Kihara Toshie, "Kanō Tan'yū's *Gakuko-jō* and the *Ryusho Tegami*," in *Art History Cross-Sections* (edited by the Takeda Tsuneo 70th Birthday Commemoration Association), Seibundō, 1995.
- ⁸ Mitsuhsa Takayanagi, Taishi Okayama, Kazuma Saiki, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokeifu*, Zoku Gunsho Ruijū Kansei-kai, 1964–1967, vol. 14.
- ⁹ Katsumi Kuroita, National History Compilation Committee, *Tokugawa Jikki*, Yoshikawa Kobunkan, 1976, vol. 5. Masakatsu's father, Masanori, initially served Toyotomi Hideyoshi and was stationed at Nagoya Castle in Hizen Province during the Bunroku Campaign. In the Battle of Sekigahara, he joined the Eastern Army and defeated Onodera Tsunamoto before meeting Tokugawa Ieyasu and Hidetada in Osaka, where he was granted a sword. The Rokugō family received Honjō Castle in Genwa 9, and the castle town prospered through trade along the Omono River.
- ¹⁰ See Note 8, *Newly Revised Kansei Chōshū Shokeifu*, vol. 12, and Note 9, *Tokugawa Jikki*, vol. 4, 1976.
- ¹¹ This "Cat Painting" is also referenced in the *Ryuei Gohonzakura: Copper Storage Hanging Scrolls and Poetry Records* (held by the Tokyo National Research Institute for Cultural Properties), which states: "Kanbun 4, Dragon, July 13 - One painting of a cat by Emperor Huizong, a relic of Uesugi Harima-dono, designated as a famous work" (Mayumi Ono &

- Chizuko Emi, "Ryuei Gohonzakura: Copper Storage Hanging Scrolls and Poetry Records – Transcription and Commentary," *Art Research* 425, 2018).
- ¹² Previously cited note 6, Sakakibara, pp. 615–617.
- ¹³ Motoaki Kono, "Tan'yū Shukuzu: Centered on the Hirafuku Family Collection," *Kobijutsu* 60, 1981. Also see the same author's *Nihon no Bijutsu 194: Kanō Tan'yū*, Shibundō, 1982. Kono summarized the purposes of Tan'yū Shukuzu production into three categories: "for his own creative activities," "as reference materials for authentication," and "as teaching materials for his disciples."
- ¹⁴ Previously cited note 7, Kihara, p. 111; previously cited note 6, Mito, p. 121.
- ¹⁵ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 18.
- ¹⁶ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 6.
- ¹⁷ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 14.
- ¹⁸ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 21.
- ¹⁹ Timon Screech (translated by Jin Matsushima), "Kanō Tan'yū and the Dutch East India Company," *Kokka* 1402, 2012.
- ²⁰ Previously cited note 4, Mr. Kadowaki, p. 139. Kadowaki pointed out an article in *Inaba Nikki* mentioning Tan'yū and Takagi Sakuemon attending a gathering at the residence of Inaba Masanori.
- ²¹ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 13.
- ²² *Zue Hōkan Zokuhen*, Vol. 6.
- ²³ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 2.
- ²⁴ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 10.
- ²⁵ Mayumi Ono, "Research Note: Kanō Tan'yū's *Sōka Shaseizu*—Chronological Trends in the Collected Sketches and the Providers of Subjects," *MUSEUM* 657, 2015, pp. 54–56; previously cited note 4, Kadowaki, pp. 134–142.
- ²⁶ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 11.
- ²⁷ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 1.
- ²⁸ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 11.
- ²⁹ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 5.
- ³⁰ Professor Satoshi Itakura mentioned the private aspects of *Tan'yū Shukuzu*, stating that they were "sharpened precisely because they were private" and that "the fresh expressions in the *Shukuzu* allow modern viewers, who have experienced the expansion and deconstruction of classical painting frameworks, to come closest to the painter Tan'yū," suggesting that these works could even be positioned as the most representative of the era's sensibility (Satoshi Itakura, "Asian Art History from the Perspective of *Tan'yū Shukuzu*," in Yasuhiro Satō, ed., *Kōza Nihon Bijutsushi: Zuzō no Imi*, Vol. 3, University of Tokyo Press, 2005).

- ³¹ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 6.
- ³² Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 9.
- ³³ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 6.
- ³⁴ Refer to "Chikudō Sensei Ryakufu" in *Chikudō Zenshū*, compiled by Setsu Hitomi and edited by Hitomi I, held by the National Diet Library (included in *Hitomi Chikudō Shibunshū*, compiled by Shizō Hitomi, Kyūko Shoin, 1991) and Keiichi Sawai, "Introduction to *Hitomi Chikudō Shibunshū*" (included in the same volume).
- ³⁵ The name of Kanō Tsunenobu appears in more than ten illustrations even in the Kyoto National Museum version cited in note 1. In the *Baichiku Kashi* Scroll, his name appears in six illustrations, demonstrating that Tsunenobu regarded Tan'yū as his mentor in authentication.
- ³⁶ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 10.
- ³⁷ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 16.
- ³⁸ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 12.
- ³⁹ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 8.
- ⁴⁰ Andrew M. Watsky pointed out that Nichikan was recognized in Japan as an early master of grape painting, and mentioned that the museum's copy (A-5502) was a reproduction of Tan'yū's copy of Nichikan's *Grape Painting* (Andrew M. Watsky, translated by Nobue Mito, "The Phantom of Kimaru: The Main Hall of Tsukubusuma Shrine," *Bijutsu Kenkyū* 366, 1997).
- ⁴¹ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 8.
- ⁴² Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 7.
- ⁴³ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 14.
- ⁴⁴ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 14.
- ⁴⁵ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 18.
- ⁴⁶ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 6.
- ⁴⁷ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 13.
- ⁴⁸ Suntory Museum of Art, *10th Anniversary Exhibition of the Roppongi Opening: Kanō Motonobu, the Painter Who Governed the Realm*, 2017, p. 129; Tokyo University of the Arts Museum, *Sesshū: The Birth of Kiso*, 2017, p. 53.
- ⁴⁹ Previously cited note 8, *Shintei Kansei Chōshū Shokafu*, Vol. 9.
- ⁵⁰ Suntory Museum of Art, *10th Anniversary Exhibition of the Roppongi Opening: Kanō Motonobu, the Painter Who Governed the Realm*, 2017, p. 129.
- ⁵¹ Aya Ota, "Reconsidering the Provenance of the Painting Attributed to Muqi, *Radish and Turnip*," *Sannomaru Shōzōkan Yearbook & Bulletin*, Vol. 9, 2002, p. 83.
- ⁵² Teisuke Toda & Hiromitsu Ogawa, *Comprehensive Catalogue of Chinese Paintings: Supplement*, Vol. 3, Japan Edition, University of Tokyo Press, 1999, p. 93.

Postscript

The original work is: Mayumi ONO, "*Tan'yū Shukuzu* by Kano Tan'yū (Plums, Bamboo, and Sweets)", *MUSEUM* 702, pp. 21–68, November 2023. (Language: Japanese)

In the process of transcribing *Tan'yū Shukuzu*, I received valuable guidance from Mr. Yoshinori Andō (Daito Bunka University) and Dr. Jun Tanaka (Gakushuin University). I would like to express my sincere gratitude. This paper is also a result of JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number 16K02292.

Fig. 1 *Tan'yū Shukuzu (Plum, Bamboo, and Fruits Scroll)*, Upper Row, 20th Sheet

Fig. 2 *Ink Plum* by Chen Lu, Tokyo National Museum

Fig. 3 *Tan'yū Shukuzu (Plum, Bamboo, and Sweets Scroll)*, Upper Row, 21st Sheet

Fig. 4 Same, Lower Row, 1st Sheet

Fig. 5 Same, Lower Row, 66th Sheet

Fig. 6 *Loquat Painting* by Kanō Tan'yū,

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Fig. 7 *Tan'yū Shukuzu*, Upper Row, 1st Sheet

Fig. 8 Same, Upper Row, 2nd Sheet

Fig. 9 Same, Upper Row, 3rd Sheet

Fig. 10 Same, Upper Row, 6th Sheet

Fig. 11 Same, Upper Row, 9th Sheet

Fig. 12 Same, Upper Row, 15th Sheet

Fig. 13 Same, Upper Row, 72nd Sheet

Fig. 14 Same, Upper Row, 34th and 35th Sheets

Fig. 15 Same, Upper Row, 36th Sheet

Fig. 16 Same, Upper Row, 37th Sheet

Fig. 17 Same, Upper Row, 41st Sheet

Fig. 18 Same, Upper Row, 42nd Sheet

Fig. 19 Same, Upper Row, 48th Sheet

Fig. 20 Same, Upper Row, 52nd Sheet

Fig. 21 Same, Upper Row, 62nd Sheet

Fig. 22 Same, Upper Row, 64th Sheet

Fig. 23 Same, Upper Row, 66th Sheet

Fig. 24 Same, Upper Row, 67th and 68th Sheets

Fig. 25 Same, Upper Row, 71st Sheet

Fig. 26 Same, Upper Row, 74th Sheet

Fig. 27 Same, Upper Row, 76th Sheet

Fig. 28 Same, Upper Row, 82nd Sheet

Fig. 29 Same, Upper Row, 84th and 85th Sheets

Fig. 30 Same, Lower Row, 5th Sheet

Fig. 31 Same, Lower Row, 8th and 9th Sheets

Fig. 32 Same, Lower Row, 42nd Sheet

Fig. 32 Same, Lower Row, 42nd Sheet

Fig. 34 Same, Lower Row, 51st Sheet

Fig. 35 Same, Lower Row, 55th Sheet

Fig. 36 Same, Lower Row, 62st Sheet

Fig. 37 Same, Lower Row, 69th Sheet

Fig. 38 Same, Upper Row, 57th Sheet

Fig. 39 Same, Upper Row, 78th Sheet

Source (except for Fig. 6): ColBase, National Institutes for Cultural Heritage, Japan. Available at: <https://colbase.nich.go.jp/>.